

Preserving Culture Through Craftsmanship: Traditional Craft Practices

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India is home to a diverse variety of historically significant crafts that date back to the Indus Valley Civilization. Indigenous people living in colonies made utilitarian items with their hands to meet their daily needs. In India, craft is a way of life. Different Indian handcrafted products are made of different materials and use various techniques. In each region they have distinctive style, design, material, tools and technique.

From earlier days, communities and villages were known by their craft practices like Pochampalli Ikat, Kutch embroidery, Banarasi Brocades, Pipli appliqué, Chennapatna wooden toy etc. The practice of handicrafts help to transfer and preserve traditions from one generation to the next. In some of the handcrafted products, with time, function and aesthetical approach has changed. (Bhand, 2012)

Different craft practices not only reflect our culture but also uplift our society by providing employment opportunities. R. N. Tagore and M. K. Gandhi have seen craft as a tool for social-upliftment and advocated for craft centric education. Their aim was to build a self-reliant and self-sufficient nation to reach its zenith.

In conclusion, in today's first-paced world we are driven by technology where most of the products we use or intake are machine made/synthetic. Due to industrialisation, many craftspeople struggle to adopt to this competition. Unorganised craft sector has resulted into young generations not practicing their traditional crafts and opting for blue collar jobs and migrating to big cities. Today, NCERT has bought Indian craft at par with other subjects by including different craft practices in school curriculum. Hence, it is important for us, to promote craft, to preserve our cultural heritage and address sustainability.

Keywords: Present paper would discuss such approaches/models.